
Research

EV-YOLO: A Next-Generation Object Detection Framework for Autonomous Electric Vehicles in Complex 2D Environments

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Abstract: This paper presents the development of an object detection algorithm tailored for electric vehicles (EVs) in complex 2D environments. The proposed EV-YOLO model enhances vehicle safety and supports advanced driver assistance systems (ADAS) through accurate and real-time detection of objects from images captured by EV cameras. By integrating novel architectural components such as Latent Context Feature Modeling (LCFM) and a Region Proposal Network with Contextual Spatial Enhancements (REPNCSPELAN-iRMB), the model achieves robust performance under diverse environmental conditions, including variations in lighting and weather. The dataset used for training consists of 1046 images, with a 70/20/10 split for training, validation, and testing. Experimental results show that EV-YOLO achieves a mean Average Precision (mAP) of 92.2%, outperforming other baseline methods in detecting objects in EV scenes. Despite the significant progress made, further research is needed to address challenges like model complexity and data generalization to new contexts. These advancements promise to improve the reliability and autonomy of electric vehicles, particularly in enhancing their integration with smart city infrastructures.

Keywords: Electric Vehicles; Deep Learning; YOLO; Object Detection,

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Introduction

The rapid development of electric vehicles (EVs) marks a significant shift in the automotive industry, driven by the need for environmentally friendly and sustainable transportation. EVs have gained widespread adoption due to their potential to reduce carbon emissions and reliance on fossil fuels. However, with the growth of the EV market, there is an increasing demand for advancements in vehicle safety, efficiency, and autonomy. Object detection plays a vital role in improving Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS), autonomous driving capabilities, and overall vehicle safety, making it a key area of research in intelligent transportation systems.

While object detection in autonomous vehicles has made significant strides, EVs operate in distinct environments, presenting unique challenges. EVs interact with infrastructure specific to their operation, such as charging stations,

electric grids, and specialized parking areas. These complexities, combined with diverse environmental conditions like rain, snow, fog, and low-light scenarios, make object detection more difficult. Traditional detection systems often struggle with issues like glare, small or distant objects, and irregular orientations that are common in EV environments. To address these challenges, this research introduces EV-YOLO, a model specifically designed for 2D object detection in EV environments. While leveraging the efficiency and real-time performance of the popular YOLO framework, EV-YOLO incorporates advanced techniques to improve accuracy and robustness under diverse driving conditions. Key innovations include Latent Context Feature Modeling (LCFM) and a Region Proposal Network with Contextual Spatial Enhancements and Attention Mechanisms (REPNCSPELAN-iRMB), which optimize detection precision regardless of object orientation or scene complexity. Transfer learning is employed to enhance generalization across various datasets. The dataset for training and validation consists of over 1,000 images, capturing a wide range of environmental conditions. The model also integrates attention mechanisms to improve focus on critical regions, ensuring higher accuracy and efficiency in object detection. Beyond vehicle safety, accurate detection plays a crucial role in enabling EVs to interact seamlessly with smart city infrastructure, contributing to better traffic management, reduced congestion, and optimized energy use. This integration supports broader sustainability goals and enhances the efficiency of urban transportation systems.

Impact Statement

The development of the EV-YOLO object detection algorithm significantly advances the field of autonomous electric vehicles (EVs) by enhancing their ability to accurately detect and classify objects in complex 2D environments. This breakthrough has the potential to improve road safety by enabling more reliable and efficient Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) in EVs. By integrating robust deep learning techniques and addressing real-world challenges such as variable lighting, weather conditions, and orientation of objects, this research contributes to the broader goals of reducing traffic accidents and enhancing autonomous driving systems. Additionally, the model's ability to integrate seamlessly with smart city infrastructure, such as charging stations and traffic management systems, supports the ongoing transition to more sustainable, intelligent urban transportation networks. The EV-YOLO algorithm's improvements in object detection accuracy and real-time performance pave the way for safer, more efficient, and autonomous electric vehicles, contributing to the future of smart and sustainable mobility solutions.

Literature Review

Object detection plays a critical role in autonomous driving and electric vehicle (EV) safety, driving significant advancements in vehicle technology and the development of intelligent transportation systems. With the rise of electric vehicles, researchers have focused on enhancing object detection models to improve accuracy and robustness in various driving environments. The increasing complexity of real-world scenarios, such as changing weather conditions, diverse lighting, and the presence of EV-specific infrastructure like charging stations, has motivated the development of more specialized object detection algorithms. In this section, we review the most relevant research contributions in the field of object detection, focusing on the evolution of deep learning models, the challenges specific to EV environments, and the methodologies used to improve detection accuracy and efficiency.

1. Object Detection in Electric Vehicles and Autonomous Driving

The rise of electric vehicles (EVs) and autonomous driving has increased demand for efficient object detection systems, essential for Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) and vehicle safety. Dai et al. [1] emphasized the importance of accurate 2D object detection in EVs for identifying traffic signs, pedestrians, and vehicles. Similarly, Chen et al. [2] introduced a Hybrid ResNet Lite and Cascade Pyramid RCNN approach for 2D LiDAR-based detection in autonomous driving. Recent studies, like Gragnaniello et al. [3], have advanced multi-object detection with ConvNext and QDTrack,

while Xiao et al. [4] used multi-sensor fusion to enhance near-field object detection, improving ADAS accuracy and reliability.

2. Deep Learning for Object Detection

Deep learning models have significantly improved object detection, with the YOLO framework becoming popular for its real-time performance. Redmon et al. [5] introduced YOLO, which became a benchmark due to its ability to predict object locations and classifications in a single pass. Subsequent versions, like YOLOv4 by Bochkovskiy et al. [6], further enhanced accuracy and efficiency. However, traditional YOLO models still struggle in complex environments like those encountered by electric vehicles, particularly with small or distant objects and challenging conditions like rain, fog, or low light. These limitations highlight the need for specialized algorithms tailored to EV-specific environments.

3. Object Detection Challenges in Electric Vehicle Environments

The operational environment of electric vehicles (EVs) presents unique challenges for object detection. Unlike traditional vehicles, EVs often interact with specialized infrastructure like charging stations and electric grids, while also facing tough conditions such as inclement weather, low light, and reflective surfaces. These factors require more robust and flexible detection models for real-world EV settings.

Zhang et al. [7] highlighted that models like YOLO often struggle with small objects and varying angles, emphasizing the need for orientation-aware detection systems. Standard models using horizontal bounding boxes are insufficient for capturing EV-specific objects like charging stations. Reflective surfaces on modern EVs can cause glare, complicating detection, especially in bright or low-light environments. Researchers are addressing these issues by integrating attention mechanisms and context-aware features to improve detection accuracy in such complex conditions.

4. Advances in Deep Learning for EV Object Detection

Several innovative approaches have emerged to address the challenges of EV object detection. Specialized deep learning models have significantly improved accuracy, robustness, and real-time performance. Integrating attention mechanisms into these models enhances detection by focusing on critical regions in complex environments.

Transfer learning has also proven effective, allowing models to leverage pre-trained weights, improving generalization and reducing the need for large labeled datasets. Zhang et al. [8] demonstrated its value in enhancing EV object detection. Additionally, novel architectural advancements, such as Latent Context Feature Modeling (LCFM) and Region Proposal Network with Contextual Enhancements (REPNCSPPELAN-iRMB) in EV-YOLO, enable better feature extraction, improving detection in diverse orientations and conditions, crucial for EV environments.

5. Comparative Analysis of Object Detection Models

Several baseline methods have been used to assess object detection in EV environments. Faster R-CNN, proposed by Ren et al. [9], is known for high detection accuracy but is slow, making it unsuitable for real-time applications. CenterNet, introduced by Zhou et al. [10], offers faster performance, ideal for real-time detection, but struggles with small or distant objects in complex settings.

YOLOv9 improved real-time detection with better feature extraction and multi-scale fusion, making it effective for EV environments. However, traditional models, including YOLOv9, still face challenges in EV-specific scenarios. EV-YOLO integrates YOLOv9's strengths with new architectural components, providing a more robust solution for EV object detection.

Dataset Collection

The dataset collection process is a crucial step in the development of robust and accurate object detection models, especially for electric vehicles (EVs), where the diversity of objects, environmental conditions, and unique infrastructure elements demand high-quality, well-annotated data. For the EV-YOLO model, a comprehensive and diverse dataset was collected to ensure that the model can generalize well across different real-world driving conditions and various EV-specific environments. This section provides a detailed overview of the dataset collection process, including the image sources, data annotation, dataset characteristics, and data preprocessing techniques employed to prepare the dataset for training and evaluation.

1. Image Source

The dataset for training and evaluating the EV-YOLO model was compiled from various online sources, including automotive websites, EV charging station directories, open-source autonomous driving datasets, and other platforms. This collection strategy ensured diversity in the 2D images of electric vehicles, covering a wide range of scenes, lighting conditions, weather, and vehicle types. The images depict common EV scenarios such as highways, urban streets, parking lots, rural areas, and EV-specific infrastructure like charging stations. Diverse objects, such as pedestrians, traffic signs, and vehicles, were included to train the model for real-world challenges. To ensure robustness, images were sourced globally from both developed and developing countries, capturing regional differences in EV infrastructure and environmental conditions.

Figure: Diverse Examples of Dataset

2. Dataset Composition

The dataset contains 1046 images of various electric vehicles, objects, and environmental elements. It was divided into 665 images (70%) for training, 285 images (20%) for validation, and 96 images (10%) for testing, ensuring a diverse set for training and evaluation. It includes a range of vehicle types such as electric cars, buses, trucks, ambulances, minibuses, and specialized EVs like zips and electric taxis, enabling the model to differentiate between vehicles and non-vehicle objects like infrastructure and pedestrians in complex scenes. The dataset also covers EV-specific infrastructure, such as charging stations, electric grids, and smart traffic systems, along with various environmental conditions, including different lighting and weather scenarios, ensuring robustness in real-world driving.

Dataset analysis shows its diversity:

- 679 images of cars (58.2%)
- 190 images of microbuses (16.3%)
- 89 images of buses (7.6%)
- 59 images of ambulances (5.1%)
- 45 images of zips (3.9%)
- 104 images of other vehicles (9.0%)

3. Data Annotation

Data annotation is a critical step in preparing the dataset for training the object detection model. The images were manually annotated using the YOLO format, which is designed for bounding box-based object detection. In this format, each image is linked to a text file containing the object's class label and the coordinates of its bounding box, specifying its location within the image.

For the EV-YOLO dataset, key object categories were defined, including:

- Electric vehicles (cars, buses, trucks, microbuses, ambulances, taxis),
- Traffic signs (e.g., speed limits, pedestrian crossings, stop signs),
- Pedestrians,
- Charging stations,
- Electric grids,
- Trees and other environmental objects.

Figure: Annotation of the dataset

Each object was labeled with a bounding box indicating its precise location. For instance, electric vehicles were annotated with purple boxes, houses with green, trees with orange, and electric grids with yellow. The manual annotation process ensured accuracy, providing high-quality data for both training and validation. Additionally, the dataset included objects with varied orientations and scales to improve the model's detection capabilities across different distances and angles. Electric vehicles were annotated from multiple perspectives, including front, rear, side, and top-down views. This diversity in orientation is vital for training the model to manage real-world driving scenarios where objects can appear in unexpected positions or orientations.

Adversarial and Environmental Challenges

The dataset includes adversarial conditions to simulate real-world challenges EVs may face, such as haze, fog, rain, bright sunlight, glare, and nighttime conditions. These scenarios reduce visibility and make object recognition harder, testing the robustness of the EV-YOLO model. For example, fog can blur or obscure objects like vehicles and traffic signs, while glare from reflective surfaces may cause false positives. These conditions ensure the model is trained to handle challenging environments and improve detection in non-ideal situations.

Data Preprocessing and Augmentation: To enhance the model's robustness, various preprocessing and augmentation techniques were applied. Each image was resized to 640x640 pixels for consistency and efficient batch processing. Data augmentation methods like rotation, scaling, flipping, and random cropping were used to increase data variability, improving the model's ability to generalize and handle changes in object orientation, size, and position.

Research Methodology

The research methodology of this paper involves a comprehensive approach to developing the EV-YOLO object detection model, which is specifically designed to address the challenges faced by electric vehicles (EVs) in complex 2D environments. This section covers the motivations for the study, the architecture of the EV-YOLO model, the data collection and preprocessing techniques used, and the detailed training and inference pipeline for model implementation. The methodology also includes a set of mathematical equations used for evaluating the model's performance, which are crucial for understanding how the object detection system was optimized and assessed.

1. Motivations

The rapid adoption of electric vehicles has brought forth unique challenges in vehicle safety and object detection, particularly due to the diverse and unpredictable nature of real-world driving conditions. EVs operate in environments that often differ from traditional internal combustion engine vehicles, such as around charging stations, electric grids, and smart traffic systems. This requires more sophisticated object detection algorithms capable of handling environmental factors like lighting variability, weather conditions, and object orientations. In response to these challenges, the EV-YOLO model was designed to provide robust 2D object detection tailored specifically for electric vehicle operations, integrating state-of-the-art deep learning techniques to improve detection accuracy and efficiency [11].

2. Overview of the EV-YOLO Architecture

The proposed EV-YOLO model builds upon the architecture of YOLOv9, incorporating several novel components that enhance its feature extraction and multi-scale fusion capabilities. The architecture introduces two key modules: Rep4 with Inverted Residual Mobile Block (iRMB) and the SFNeck with advanced feature alignment and attention mechanisms, which are designed to address the unique challenges posed by EV environments.

Figure : Architecture of EV-YOLO

2.1. Rep4 with iRMB Module

The Rep4 module integrates the inverted Residual Mobile Block (iRMB), which enhances feature extraction by focusing on essential details and suppressing redundant information. The iRMB module in the architecture works to invert deep semantic information while removing unnecessary features. The architecture of this module is depicted by the following equation:

$$F_{fuse} = RepBlock(F_{align})$$

In this equation, F_{fuse} represents the fused feature output from the RepBlock module, which receives aligned features F_{align} as input. This operation enables the model to extract richer semantic information while reducing computational overhead [12].

Figure: General Architecture of iRMB

2.2. SFNeck (YOLOv9-REP4-SFNeck)

The SFNeck introduces a gather-and-distribute mechanism that facilitates the effective fusion of multi-scale features. This mechanism consists of two branches: the shallow gather-and-distribute branch for low-level feature extraction and the deep gather-and-distribute branch for high-level feature extraction. Each branch comprises three core components:

1. Information Fusion Module (IFM),
2. Information Injection Module, and
3. Feature Alignment Module (FAM).

For efficient alignment of features across layers, the Low-order Feature Alignment Module (Low-FAM) uses average pooling to downsample the input features. The aligned feature F_{align} is generated by downsampling and is expressed by the following equation:

$$F_{align} = Low_FAM([B2, B3, B4, B5])$$

where $[B2, B3, B4, B5]$ represents the features from various layers of the model. The feature fusion operation combines multi-level features using reparameterized convolutional blocks (RepBlocks) to generate F_{fuse} [13].

Figure: Architecture of SF Neck

The SFNeck design also incorporates attention mechanisms to highlight critical regions within the images. This improves the detection accuracy by focusing the model’s attention on objects of interest while ignoring background noise or irrelevant details.

3. Dataset Collection and Preprocessing

The dataset used for training and evaluating the EV-YOLO model was collected from various online sources, comprising a total of 1046 images of electric vehicles and their environments. The dataset included images with diverse lighting conditions, weather variations, and object orientations, making it ideal for developing a robust object detection model for real-world scenarios. Data augmentation techniques, including rotation, scaling, and flipping, were applied to increase the variability of the training data and improve the model’s ability to generalize. All images were resized to a uniform resolution of 640x640 pixels to match the input size required by the YOLO architecture. This resizing ensured that the model could process the images consistently and efficiently [14].

4. Training and Inference Pipeline

The EV-YOLO model was trained using the PyTorch framework on GPU-accelerated hardware to optimize both accuracy and real-time performance. The training pipeline involved several key steps, including the initialization of model parameters, backpropagation of error gradients, and optimization of the network using the Adam optimizer.

4.1. Training Process

The training process involved feeding the annotated dataset into the model, where the input images were passed through multiple convolutional layers and attention mechanisms to extract feature maps. The model's loss function was defined as a combination of classification loss, bounding box regression loss, and confidence loss, ensuring that the model learned to accurately detect and classify objects. The total loss L is calculated as:

$$L = L_{cls} + L_{bbox} + L_{conf}$$

where L_{cls} represents the classification loss, L_{bbox} is the bounding box regression loss, and L_{conf} denotes the confidence loss for the object detection task [15].

The Adam optimizer was used to adjust the model's weights during training, with an initial learning rate of 0.01. The optimization process followed the gradient descent approach, where the gradients of the loss function were computed and used to update the model's weights. The learning rate was dynamically adjusted using a step decay strategy based on the validation performance after each epoch. The model was trained for 150 epochs with a batch size of 4 to ensure convergence and minimize overfitting.

4.2. Performance Metrics

To evaluate the model's performance, several metrics were employed, including precision, recall, F1-score, and mean Average Precision (mAP). Precision and recall are calculated as follows:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Positives}}$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Negatives}}$$

The F1-score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall and is calculated by:

$$\text{F1-score} = \frac{2 \times \text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

The mean Average Precision (mAP) is computed as the average of the average precision (AP) for each class in the dataset. The AP for a single class is the area under the precision-recall curve and is given by:

$$\text{AP} = \int_0^1 \text{Precision}(r) dr$$

The **mAP** is the mean of the AP values for all object classes:

$$\text{mAP} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \text{AP}_i$$

where N represents the total number of object classes [16].

4.3. Inference Pipeline

After training, the model was deployed for real-time object detection. During inference, it processes input images using the trained network without updating parameters. The pipeline follows the same architecture but operates in a forward-only mode, using learned weights to predict object classes and bounding boxes. For each image, the model outputs detected objects, bounding box coordinates, and confidence scores. Objects with scores above a threshold are classified as true detections, enabling real-time object detection, crucial for autonomous driving and vehicle safety.

This methodology showcases the development of the EV-YOLO model, using advanced deep learning, attention mechanisms, and transfer learning to improve object detection. The optimized architecture and training ensure it performs well in complex EV environments, enhancing autonomous driving safety and efficiency.

Experiments and Results

In this section, we present the experimental setup, evaluation metrics, baseline methods for comparison, and an organized analysis of the results obtained from the training and testing of the **EV-YOLO** model. The experiments focus on evaluating the model's object detection accuracy, computational efficiency, and robustness in complex electric vehicle (EV) environments.

1. Experimental Setup

To thoroughly assess the performance of the EV-YOLO model, a comprehensive experimental setup was devised. The dataset comprised 1046 images, collected from various sources, featuring diverse real-world conditions that electric vehicles typically encounter. These images included various object types such as vehicles, pedestrians, traffic signs, charging stations, and electric grids. The dataset was split into three subsets: 665 images (70%) for training, 285 images (20%) for validation, and 96 images (10%) for testing [17].

The experiments were carried out using Google Colab with access to an NVIDIA A100 GPU, which significantly accelerated the training process. The implementation was done using Python 3.12 and the PyTorch deep learning framework, which facilitated efficient parallel processing of computations and optimized model training [18]. The training process spanned 150 epochs, with a batch size of 4 and an initial learning rate of 0.01, dynamically adjusted using a step decay schedule based on validation performance [19].

Data preprocessing included resizing all images to 640x640 pixels, and data augmentation techniques such as rotation, scaling, color jittering, and flipping were employed to increase the variability of the training data. This ensured that the model could generalize well to new and unseen data, particularly in challenging scenarios with different lighting and weather conditions.

Baseline Methods

To effectively demonstrate the performance improvements of EV-YOLO, several baseline object detection models were used for comparison:

- **Faster R-CNN:** A widely-used object detection model that incorporates a Region Proposal Network (RPN) to suggest object regions before classification. Although accurate, it is slower than other models for real-time detection [21].
- **CenterNet:** A keypoint-based object detection model that detects objects as center points and predicts their size and offset. CenterNet is known for its speed and efficiency in real-time applications [22].
- **YOLOv9:** The latest iteration of the YOLO (You Only Look Once) model, known for its fast real-time detection capabilities. YOLOv9 serves as the foundation for the EV-YOLO model and offers a robust framework for object detection in real-time scenarios [23].

The performance of the proposed EV-YOLO model was compared against these baselines to highlight its advantages in terms of detection accuracy, speed, and robustness in electric vehicle environments.

4. Experimental Results

The results of the experiments are detailed below, highlighting the effectiveness of the EV-YOLO model compared to baseline methods.

4.1. YOLOv9 Performance

The YOLOv9 model, used as the foundation for EV-YOLO, was evaluated using the dataset, and its performance was measured based on precision, recall, F1-score, and mAP. The results demonstrated that YOLOv9 was able to detect objects with a high degree of accuracy, achieving a **mAP@0.5 of 89.9%**, showing its capability to accurately detect and classify objects in various scenarios. However, YOLOv9 faced challenges in detecting small or distant objects, especially under difficult environmental conditions, such as low lighting or glare [24].

4.2. Faster R-CNN and CenterNet Performance

Faster R-CNN performed well in terms of detection accuracy, achieving an mAP@0.5 of 88.1%, but it lagged behind YOLOv9 in terms of real-time detection speed due to the computational complexity of its region proposal process. While it was more accurate in detecting small objects, its slower speed made it less suitable for real-time electric vehicle applications [25].

CenterNet, on the other hand, performed faster than Faster R-CNN and achieved competitive accuracy with an mAP@0.5 of 87.3%. Its speed and efficiency in detecting objects in real-time environments made it suitable for EV applications, but it still faced limitations in detecting occluded or oriented objects in complex scenes [26].

4.3. EV-YOLO Performance

The EV-YOLO model demonstrated significant improvements over the baseline models. The incorporation of the Rep4 with iRMB module and the SFNeck architecture enhanced the feature extraction process, enabling the model to capture detailed semantic information. The attention mechanisms further allowed the model to focus on critical regions, improving detection in adverse conditions, such as low lighting or rainy weather.

The EV-YOLO model achieved an mAP@0.5 of 92.2%, outperforming YOLOv9 and the other baseline models. The precision and recall scores were also higher, with an F1-score of 0.91, indicating a strong balance between precision and recall. The improvements in mAP and F1-score highlight the model's superior performance in real-world EV environments, where object detection accuracy is critical for safety and autonomy.

Figure : Training and Validation Visualization of EV-YOLO Model

The following table summarizes the performance of all models across key metrics:

Model	mAP@0.5	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Faster R-CNN	88.1%	0.85	0.84	0.84
CenterNet	87.3%	0.83	0.86	0.84
YOLOv9	89.9%	0.88	0.87	0.88
EV-YOLO	92.2%	0.91	0.90	0.91

4.4. Performance under Adverse Conditions

One of the key objectives of EV-YOLO was to improve detection performance in challenging conditions. The experiments conducted on images captured in rainy, foggy, and low-light environments showed that the EV-YOLO model maintained a high level of accuracy even under adverse conditions. For example, the mAP for images taken in low-light conditions was 90.7%, compared to 85.6% for YOLOv9 and 82.4% for Faster R-CNN. The attention mechanism integrated into the EV-YOLO model enabled it to focus on essential features, improving its robustness in such scenarios [27].

The experimental results indicate that the EV-YOLO model outperforms traditional object detection models in several key areas. Its superior mAP, precision, and recall scores make it highly effective for electric vehicle object detection, particularly in complex and dynamic environments. The novel architectural improvements, including the Rep4 module and SFNeck, played a crucial role in enhancing detection accuracy while maintaining real-time performance. Furthermore, the model's ability to operate effectively in low-light and adverse weather conditions underscores its potential for improving safety in autonomous electric vehicles.

Experimental Result Analysis and Discussion

This section provides a comprehensive analysis of the experimental results obtained from the EV-YOLO model, along with a detailed discussion of the model's performance across various scenarios and its comparison with baseline

methods. The analysis focuses on the model's accuracy, speed, robustness in challenging conditions, and overall efficiency in real-world electric vehicle (EV) environments.

1. Analysis of Experimental Results

The EV-YOLO model was evaluated using a diverse dataset of electric vehicle environments, and its performance was compared against well-known baseline models, including Faster R-CNN, CenterNet, and YOLOv9. The results demonstrate significant improvements in detection accuracy, robustness in complex environments, and computational efficiency.

1.1. Accuracy and Precision

The EV-YOLO model achieved a mean Average Precision (mAP)_{@0.5} of 92.2%, outperforming all baseline models. This improvement can be attributed to the incorporation of advanced architectural components, such as the Rep4 with iRMB and SFNeck modules, which enhance feature extraction and multi-scale fusion, leading to more accurate detection of objects under varying conditions. The high precision of 0.91 and recall of 0.90 indicate that the model successfully reduces false positives and false negatives, making it highly reliable for detecting objects in real-world EV scenarios [28]. In comparison, the YOLOv9 model achieved a mAP_{@0.5} of 89.9%, which, although respectable, demonstrated limitations in handling small or distant objects, particularly under challenging environmental conditions such as glare or fog. The Faster R-CNN model, despite its high accuracy (mAP_{@0.5} of 88.1%), was slower and struggled in real-time detection applications, making it less suitable for deployment in electric vehicles where quick decision-making is critical [29]. CenterNet performed comparably to Faster R-CNN, with an mAP_{@0.5} of 87.3%, but also faced challenges in detecting oriented or occluded objects [30].

1.2. F1-Score and Generalization

The F1-score for EV-YOLO was 0.91, demonstrating a well-balanced model that effectively trades off between precision and recall. This high F1-score reflects the model's capacity to generalize across diverse object categories, ranging from vehicles and pedestrians to EV-specific infrastructure like charging stations and electric grids. The strong F1-score underscores the model's ability to operate efficiently across different EV environments, which often include occluded objects, varying lighting, and fluctuating traffic conditions [31].

1.3. Computational Efficiency

The EV-YOLO model was optimized for real-time detection, achieving superior performance compared to Faster R-CNN, which is known for its slower inference time due to the Region Proposal Network (RPN). EV-YOLO's architecture enables faster detection without compromising accuracy, making it ideal for autonomous electric vehicle applications where real-time processing is essential.

The integration of the Rep4 module improved the model's computational efficiency by reparameterizing feature extraction, which reduces unnecessary computations and enhances processing speed. During testing, EV-YOLO demonstrated an average inference time of 15 ms per image, compared to 45 ms for Faster R-CNN and 22 ms for CenterNet, highlighting the model's suitability for real-time applications in dynamic traffic environments [32].

2. Performance in Challenging Environmental Conditions

The EV-YOLO model was specifically designed to handle adverse environmental conditions, such as low-light, fog, rain, and glare, which are commonly encountered in real-world EV driving scenarios. The following subsections detail the model's performance under these conditions and provide insights into the impact of these challenges on detection accuracy.

2.1. Low-Light Conditions

In low-light conditions, object detection becomes particularly challenging due to reduced visibility and increased noise in the images. The attention mechanism incorporated into EV-YOLO allowed the model to focus on relevant areas of the image, effectively filtering out irrelevant information and improving detection accuracy. The model achieved a mAP@0.5 of 90.7% in low-light conditions, outperforming YOLOv9 (85.6%) and Faster R-CNN (82.4%) [33].

The attention mechanism ensured that the model concentrated on object features with higher contrast, such as vehicle headlights or traffic signs, which are critical for safe navigation in low-light environments. This capability makes EV-YOLO highly effective for nighttime driving and other low-visibility scenarios often encountered by electric vehicles.

2.2. Fog and Rain

Fog and rain introduce additional challenges by obscuring objects, creating reflections, and reducing overall image clarity. Despite these challenges, the EV-YOLO model maintained a high level of accuracy, achieving an mAP@0.5 of 88.5% in foggy conditions and 89.2% in rainy conditions. In comparison, YOLOv9 recorded mAP scores of 82.9% and 84.7% respectively, while Faster R-CNN struggled the most, with mAP scores of 80.3% in fog and 81.6% in rain [34].

The EV-YOLO model's robustness in these conditions is primarily due to the multi-scale feature fusion and contextual spatial enhancements introduced in the SFNeck module, which enable the model to retain key object features even in degraded image quality conditions. This demonstrates the model's capacity to operate effectively under adverse weather conditions, which is critical for autonomous driving applications.

2.3. Glare and Reflective Surfaces

Reflective surfaces, especially on modern electric vehicles, can cause glare, which affects the performance of traditional object detection algorithms. The attention mechanism within EV-YOLO played a crucial role in mitigating the impact of glare by focusing on the most relevant features of the objects, ignoring bright spots or reflections caused by sunlight or artificial lighting. As a result, EV-YOLO achieved a mAP@0.5 of 91.4% in images affected by glare, outperforming YOLOv9 (87.8%) and Faster R-CNN (83.5%) [35].

3. Comparison with Baseline Methods

In comparison with the baseline methods, the EV-YOLO model consistently outperformed Faster R-CNN, CenterNet, and YOLOv9 across all evaluation metrics. Faster R-CNN, although highly accurate, was significantly slower and less efficient in real-time detection tasks, making it unsuitable for autonomous electric vehicle applications. CenterNet, on the other hand, offered faster detection but struggled with complex object orientations and occlusions, leading to lower overall accuracy.

YOLOv9, the foundation upon which EV-YOLO was built, performed admirably but fell short in challenging environmental conditions, particularly in detecting small or distant objects. The integration of Rep4 with iRMB and SFNeck modules in EV-YOLO addressed these shortcomings by enhancing feature extraction and enabling better handling of multi-scale objects, occlusions, and environmental adversities. These enhancements led to substantial improvements in both mAP and real-time performance.

4. Discussion of Results

The results of the experiments demonstrate that the EV-YOLO model successfully addresses the challenges specific to electric vehicle environments. The superior performance of the model in terms of mAP, precision, recall, and F1-score confirms that the architectural innovations introduced in EV-YOLO, including the Rep4 with iRMB module and SFNeck, provide significant improvements in detection accuracy and computational efficiency.

The ability of the model to operate effectively in real-time, while maintaining high accuracy under adverse conditions such as low light, rain, fog, and glare, makes it a highly suitable candidate for integration into electric vehicles and autonomous driving systems. Furthermore, the attention mechanism and multi-scale feature fusion enhance the model's robustness, allowing it to accurately detect objects in complex and dynamic environments, which are common in real-world EV scenarios.

The performance comparison with baseline methods highlights EV-YOLO's superiority, especially in challenging conditions where traditional models tend to falter. The architectural enhancements of EV-YOLO not only improved detection accuracy but also ensured that the model could meet the real-time processing requirements critical for autonomous vehicle applications.

Conclusion

This research presents the development and evaluation of the EV-YOLO model, an advanced object detection framework specifically designed for electric vehicle (EV) environments. The model addresses key challenges such as varying object orientations, adverse weather conditions, low lighting, and complex urban settings that electric vehicles encounter in real-world scenarios. Through the integration of innovative architectural components like the Rep4 with iRMB module and the SFNeck, EV-YOLO demonstrated significant improvements in detection accuracy, computational efficiency, and robustness compared to traditional models such as YOLOv9, Faster R-CNN, and CenterNet.

The model achieved a mAP@0.5 of 92.2%, outperforming baseline methods across multiple performance metrics, including precision, recall, and F1-score, while maintaining real-time processing capabilities. These results confirm that the enhancements introduced in EV-YOLO, particularly the attention mechanisms and multi-scale feature fusion, enable it to handle complex and dynamic environments more effectively than previous object detection models.

Moreover, the model's ability to perform well in challenging conditions such as fog, rain, glare, and low-light scenarios demonstrates its robustness and suitability for deployment in autonomous driving systems. The EV-YOLO model's real-time inference speed of 15 ms per image further makes it an ideal solution for electric vehicles, where timely and accurate detection of objects is critical for safety and navigation.

In conclusion, the EV-YOLO model offers a significant contribution to the field of autonomous driving and electric vehicle safety. Its superior performance in real-world conditions, coupled with its computational efficiency, positions it as a highly effective framework for improving the object detection capabilities of modern electric vehicles. Future work can focus on extending the model's capabilities to include 3D object detection and exploring its integration with other sensor modalities such as LiDAR and radar to further enhance its performance in complex environments.

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